

D6.4

Communication & dissemination plan update

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AEC	Asociación Española de la Carretera – Spanish Road Association
CINEA	European Cimate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CSuM	Conference on Sustainable Urban Mobility
D	Deliverable
DTFL	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
ICOOR	Interuniversity Consortium for Organisation and Operations Research
ITS	Intelligent Tarnsportations Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PM	Project Month
QR	Quick Response
SC	Steering Committee
STA	Smart Transportation Alliance
TRA	Transport Research Arena
UAE	United Arab Emirates
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UNIMORE	University of Modena and Reggio Emilia
UPM	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid – Technical University of Madrid
USA	United States of America
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines the progress made by the KEYSTONE consortium from the beginning of the project (in June 2023, M1) to the mid-term point of the project (covering up to November 2024, M18). It details all efforts related to the communication of project activities and the dissemination of both preliminary and final project results.

It should be noted that the report goes beyond the pre-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established during the proposal stage. It also seeks to update the reader on new, additional activities and measures undertaken by the consortium, consistently choosing the best and most effective communication tool to ensure the successful dissemination of results – which is the ultimate goal of KEYSTONE’s Work Package (WP) 6.

While the WP6 – *Communication, Dissemination, Replication and Exploitation* - and, in particular, task 6.5 – *Communication & Dissemination* - is led and coordinated by the consortium partner STA, all partners have actively contributed to the task’s objectives. Each partner selected communication channels and target groups best suited to their strengths, ensuring a broad outreach while targeting highly relevant group of audiences, including subscribers, followers, partners, and allies.

In terms of the KPIs, the project’s communication & dissemination is overperforming, exceeding expectations. In nearly all cases, the overall project’s overall targets for May 2026 have already been met 18 months ahead of schedule. Consequently, this report also offers an opportunity for the consortium to re-orient its communication & dissemination plan and activities, aim higher, and incorporate additional activities where possible.

The primary audience for this deliverable is the European Commission services and the CINEA agency, who will evaluate and assess the progress of KEYSTONE. However, it may also serve other initiatives and projects as inspiration on how to plan, execute, adapt and improve excellent communication & dissemination strategies.

2. Introduction

Within the scope of the KEYSTONE project, this deliverable aims to provide a detailed overview of the communication & dissemination activities conducted up to the halfway point of the project - Project Month 18 (PM18). It describes the tools used and all the necessary activities undertaken within these first 18 months of project execution. Following the methodology outlined in the previous D6.3, this report also aims to ensure the highest possible outreach within the duration of the project which began on June 1, 2023 and ends on May 31, 2026.

The report also presents a detailed update on the efforts made by all KEYSTONE partners to enhance the project activities. Since the communication & dissemination activities are shared tasks among consortium partners, their cooperation and inputs have been critical to guarantee the successful and effective communication and dissemination of project results.

Although the project is only at its midpoint, the communication and dissemination activities have been remarkably successful. Project partners have actively participated in various events and engaged with stakeholders from different industries, as well as with individuals from targeted audiences, to showcase project activities and latest updates of the project. Most of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been reached - not only for the halfway mark but also for the overall project duration - due to the partners' high engagement and close collaboration. Furthermore, the internal communication among project partners has been proven to be highly efficient and productive, further enhancing the project's outreach and impact.

3. Reporting

To document this remarkable performance, it is essential to review the original planning for the communication & dissemination measures, as outlined at the proposal stage and later refined within the previous D6.3. The results in the Table below are clear: the column labeled as *PM 18 (Reporting)* contains the current status of the KPIs up to October 31, 2024. The results are colour-coded when compared to the final target of M36 (the overall project target):

- **Green:** The KPI has been reached for the entire project duration;
- **Grey:** The KPI is performing well and has reached its planned intermediate target;
- **Blue:** The KPI has not been initiated.

Table 1 - Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Communication & Dissemination KPIs		PM 12 (Target)	PM 17 (Reporting)	PM 24 (Target)	PM 36 (Target)
Website	Visits / Month (Avg.)	200	2,007	250	350
	Individual Visitors	100	34,131	150	200
E-Newsletters	Editions	3	6	4	4
	Subscribers	80	85	100	120
Video Clips	Editions	-	17	1	2

Communication & Dissemination KPIs		PM 12 (Target)	PM 17 (Reporting)	PM 24 (Target)	PM 36 (Target)
Social Media	Posts	24	228= 124 (Twitter) + 104 (LinkedIn)	36	48
	Followers (All)	100	446= 122 (Twitter) + 324 (LinkedIn)	150	200
Printed Materials	Roll-Ups	1	1	-	1
	Posters	1	1	2	2
	Brochures	-	1	1	1
Publications	Conference Papers	-	2	3	3
	Journal Papers	-	-	2	2
Events	Project Events	1	3	1	1
	Attendance to External Events	3	14	5	6

A total of 11 out of the 14 KPI targets for the entire project have already been reached. Notably, some KPIs have significantly exceeded their targets, with results surpassing the original goals by factors 6 or even 170 (in the case of website visits and visitors, respectively)¹. In the following sub-sections, each KPI will be updated, and all efforts and reports will be documented accordingly. KEYSTONE consortium partners are encouraged to report all dissemination and communication activities via a dedicated Google Form designed for the reporting of the communications actions and provide a better understanding of the project’s impact. As of M17, a total of 42 communication and dissemination actions have been reported.

Figure 1 - KEYSTONE Communication & Dissemination Reporting Form

Who is the owner & manager of the action?

42 responses

¹ Ross-Hellauer, T. T., & Kraker, P. (2020). Ten simple rules for innovative dissemination of research. PLoS Comput Biol , 16.Ross-Hellauer, T. T., & Kraker, P. (2020)

4. KEYSTONE Digital Communication Tools

4.1 Website

The KEYSTONE website (<https://www.keystone-project.com/>) is the consortium's central communication & dissemination tool. Officially launched on June 20, 2023, it provides comprehensive information about the project's identity, objectives, regular updates, news, participation in events, milestones achieved, and detailed descriptions of project activities². The section *Updates* consists of the *News*, *Newsletter*, and *Media Corner* sub-categories and is the most active and updated area of the website. This section hosts all project updates, while external references to the KEYSTONE project are showcased in the *Media Corner* section. To date, 25 news items have been published on the KEYSTONE website, thanks to the active engagement of consortium partners. Below, all 26 news are listed, together with pictures that the visitor can find in the website's *News* section.

1. KEYSTONE project kicks off, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/2023-01>
2. Consortium gets together, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/2023-02-kom>
3. KEYSTONE project calls for participation (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/stakeholder-community-open-call>
4. KEYSTONE project launches a stakeholders survey (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/stakeholder-community-survey-launch>
5. KEYSTONE project at the STA Annual Conference & Innovation Awards, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/sta-conference-2023>
6. Why the digitisation of the logistics sector is overdue, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/stakeholder-survey-02>
7. Unlocking seamless transport: KEYSTONE shines at NAPCORE event, (2023) <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/event-napcore-2023>.
8. A step forward towards the digitisation of transport logistics: KEYSTONE consortium unites in Northern Italy, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/event-novara-2023>
9. KEYSTONE-FEDeRATED-FENIX-DTLF Initiatives Spearhead Knowledge Exchange at Brussels Workshop, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/knowledge-exchange-brussels-2023>
10. Towards A Sustainable EU Data Sharing Environment: KEYSTONE at the EU Data Logistics Festival, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/event-data-logistics-festival-2023>
11. The KEYSTONE Consortium wishes you Happy Holidays & a Wonderful New Year!, (2023), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/seasons-greetings>
12. Call for 1-on-1 interview open: Share your opinion!, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-stakeholders-interview-call>
13. Successful Focus Group Discussion explores challenges and opportunities in Spanish Transportation Logistics, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-focus-group-upm>
14. KEYSTONE partners attend LetExpo 2024 in Verona, Italy, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-news-letexpo>
15. Meet KEYSTONE at the Connecting Europe Days & TRA2024, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-news-ced-tra2024>
16. Revolutionising Transportation: KEYSTONE shines at Connecting Europe Days 2024, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-ced>
17. Meet KEYSTONE at the TRA2024 in Dublin, Ireland, next week! (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-news-tra>

² Epitech. (2020). Digital Communication: what is it? Concept and features. Retrieved from <https://www.epitech-it.es/digital-communication-what-is-it/>

18. KEYSTONE highlights innovations in logistics digitisation at the TRA 2024 in Dublin, Ireland, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-news-tra-2024>
19. Celebrating one year of KEYSTONE: An overview of project progress, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-altea-meeting>
20. Meet KEYSTONE at the 7th CSuM Conference in Karditsa, Greece, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-scum>.
21. KEYSTONE reveals stakeholder priorities and expectations for logistics digitisation, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-stakeholders-priorities>
22. KEYSTONE joins forces with ALICE to innovate European logistics ecosystem, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-alice-liaison>
23. KEYSTONE project takes centre stage at the 7th Sustainable Mobility Conference in Greece (CSum), (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-scum-2024>
24. Join KEYSTONE at InnoTrans 2024 in Berlin to explore stakeholders' insights on logistics digitisation (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-innotrans>
25. KEYSTONE project shares insights at the 30th ITS World Congress in Dubai (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-its>
26. Driving digital innovation ahead: KEYSTONE's impact at the InnoTrans 2024, (2024), <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/keystone-innotrans24>

Figure 2 – From left to right: i) KEYSTONE Stakeholder Community; ii) Screenshot from the piece of news on KEYSTONE's participation at the TRA in Dublin, (Ireland) on 15-18 April 2024; iii) Screenshot from the piece of news on the first FGD in Novara, (Italy), on 28 November 2023

The website has recently introduced a new section under the name *Community*, where all stakeholder's profiles are featured, highlighting their expertise and contributions toward developing a safe, sustainable, innovative, and efficient transport system for logistics and transportation in Europe. This section also includes an invitation for interest individuals to join the KEYSTONE community as members. To date, 8 stakeholder's profiles have been presented, each accompanied by a short introduction and contact details.

4.1.1 Visits per Month

The website analytics have shown to be exceptional. From its launch on June 20, 2023, until October 31, 2024, the website recorded a total of 34,131 visitors, reflecting high interest in the project and an average of 2,007 visitors per month. In the *Partners* section (<https://www.keystone-project.com/partners>), a detailed

presentation of each partner has been added, including profiles of the people involved in KEYSTONE activities from each entity. The figure below illustrates the monthly number of visitors during the first 17 months following the launch of the KEYSTONE website.

Figure 3 - Metrics of Traffic Activity of KEYSTONE Website

4.1.2 Visitors

Another metric worth investigating is the geographic distribution of website visitors, which shows engagement extending beyond Europe and the consortium network. For instance, 3,776 visitors (11.1%) are based in the United States of America (U.S.A), 932 (2.73%) in India, and 592 (1.73) in Japan³. This broad geographic reach enhances the visibility and impact of KEYSTONE’s activities. Such international engagement can foster collaborations beyond EU borders, further expanding the project’s influence. The figure below illustrates the geographic distribution of website visitors. Given this significant interest from non-EU professionals, it may make sense for the consortium to consider attending also conferences or events in these markets, such as the ITS World Congress where KEYSTONE has already participated.

Figure 4 - Geographic Distribution of KEYSTONE's Website Visitors

³ Peytom, J. (2019). What’s the Average Bounce Rate for a Website? Peytom, J. (2019)

4.2 Newsletter

The project’s newsletter, under the name *KEYSTONE In Action*, is distributed quarterly to subscribers. It includes important news, updates, milestones achieved and calls for participation to the readers. Every newsletter edition also features relevant external news pertinent to the project to provide additional value to readers. To date, 6 newsletter editions have been published, achieving the KPI target⁴. All editions are available on the KEYSTONE website in the *Newsletters* section. The release of each newsletter has been followed by additional promotion activities on KEYSTONE’s social media accounts (Linkedin and X). The figure below shows the latest edition of the *KEYSTONE In Action*.

Figure 5 - KEYSTONE In Action #4-2024

4.2.1 Newsletter Analytics

The metrics for *KEYSTONE In Action* appear to be very good, showing a significant increase over the project’s duration. The figures below demonstrate that nearly 50% of subscribers open the newsletter, highlighting that the audience is keen on receiving regular updates about KEYSTONE. As of M17, *KEYSTONE In Action* is sent to 85 subscribers, surpassing the goal of 80 subscribers for the first year of the project. It is worth mentioning that the rate of unsubscriptions is low, signifying that the content aligns well with the reader’s expectations. In the coming months, additional promotional efforts will be made both within the consortium and externally to reach the goal of 100 subscribers by the end of year 2.

⁴ Ashish, K. (2021). An empirical examination of the effects of design elements of email newsletters on consumers’ email responses and their purchase. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*.

Figure 6 - Number of KEYSTONE In Action Newsletter Subscribers

Figure 7 - Analytics of KEYSTONE In Action Newsletter

4.3 Social Media Channels

Since the start of the KEYSTONE project, two social media channels have been created (X and LinkedIn). These channels play a key role in engaging and informing the target audience while providing regular updates on the project’s progress. Both social media channels are consistently updated with diverse content, including posts, videos, images, and infographics, to ensure effective communication and dissemination to a broader audience. KEYSTONE partners have been highly active in disseminating and promoting posts by interacting and reposting them from their accounts, further amplifying KEYSTONE activities to a wider audience. To date, a total of 228 posts have been published, significantly exceeding the goal for year 1 (24 posts), and the overall project target by 140.2%. Both social media channels report significant growth, with a combined total of 446 followers, overreaching and doubling the goal for the entire project, 200 followers by M36. The success of these channels relies significantly upon the whole consortium efforts as communication and dissemination tasks are shared among the partners. In the upcoming months, we anticipate even higher growth.

4.3.1 X Channel

The X (formally Twitter) KEYSTONE profile, under the name @KEYSTONE_EU, shares content such as videos, pictures, and infographics, with a focus on visually appealing content, to align with the platform’s character limitations. The profile has shown remarkable growth in the last months, reaching 122 followers. Unfortunately, the X analytics are no longer available for free accounts, so a detailed metrics presentation of X analytics is unavailable. All partners are respectively tagged in each post to promote and facilitate reposting. The figures below show the posts published on the KEYSTONE_EU account and the number of followers.

Figure 8 - KEYSTONE_EU Posts on X

4.3.2 LinkedIn

The KEYSTONE_EU profile on LinkedIn is the most appropriate for stakeholder engagement. It has 324 followers and has achieved remarkable success thanks to the partners' contributions. All the content featured on the KEYSTONE website is shared on the KEYSTONE_EU LinkedIn profile, along with various updates, news, calls for action, and additional promotional activities. To date, more than 104 posts have been created, sharing valuable insights to a broad, targeted audience.

4.3.2.1 LinkedIn Analytics

LinkedIn has proven to be the most effective social media platform for promoting and disseminating KEYSTONE's project activities to a broader audience and the general public. The platform's analytics highlight the significant impact the project has already achieved at the halfway of its duration. As LinkedIn provides analytics for the past 12 months, the metrics are presented into two time periods. The figures for impressions are notably high, with a total of 35,867 impressions, representing the number of people who have seen the content posted.⁵ The table below shows the analytics up to M12, M17, and overall performance. In [ANNEX A](#), screenshots of the full analytics are provided.

Table 2 - LinkedIn Analytics

Metrics	PM12	PM17	Total
Impressions	20,898	14,969	35,867
Clicks	529	538	1,067
Reactions	1,067	760	1,827
Comments	22	16	38
Reposts	52	16	68
Engagement Rate	9,792	8,900	18,692

⁵ What is LinkedIn Impressions, (2024)

4.3.2.2 Social Media Campaigns

Up to M17, two social media campaigns have been launched, both of which significantly increased and positively impacted the project’s visibility. The first social media campaign was launched in M10 and lasted until M11, aimed to introduce all the project partners to the social media audience. Dedicated posts were uploaded weekly to the LinkedIn KEYSTONE account, highlighting each partner and their involvement in the project. A link was directed to the KEYSTONE dedicated Partners section, where a detailed description of each partner and the individuals involved in the project was presented. The KEYSTONE consortium demonstrated strong commitment and engagement to increase the project’s visibility by actively sharing posts from their personal and company accounts. This collective effort resulted in a tremendous boost in the project’s recognition to a broader LinkedIn audience. All project partners have shown high engagement and commitment in reposting the posts from their personal and company accounts, further amplifying KEYSTONE’s visibility. The figure below shows an example of the social media campaign and the dedicated partners’ section on the KEYSTONE website to which the posts directed users.

Figure 9 - LinkedIn Social Media Campaign & Consortium Profiles on KEYSTONE Website

The second social media campaign was launched in M14, following interviews recorded in M12 during the in-person Steering Committee (SC) meeting hosted by Etelätär Innovation in Altea, Spain. During the SC, all partners were interviewed to provide deeper insights and updates and showcase the project’s goals and future ambitions, along with each partner’s involvement. A detailed description of the videos will be provided in the Videos section, in the following category of this report.

4.4 Videos

By M17, 17 videos have been created to provide more informative, descriptive, and personalised visual content that can be addressed to a broader audience. All videos have been uploaded to the Smart Transportation Alliance's YouTube channel. The first two videos introduce the project, presenting its main activities, goals, objectives, and scope. These introductory videos are versatile and can be used in various events to address the purpose and critical issues of the KEYSTONE activities. As mentioned above, 14 interview videos were created with partner representatives to showcase each partner's role, contributions, and ambitions and increase awareness about the project among a wider audience. The videos were designed to be short and focused, using storytelling to present KEYSTONE's activities in a simple, clear, and consistent format, resulting in the most significant impact and engagement. The 17 videos have collectively received 203 views, a number expected to grow as the project continues in the following months.

Figure 10 - KEYSTONE interview series

4.5 Printed Materials

In addition to the digital communication tools established to promote the project's activities, printed materials have been designed, printed, and distributed among consortium partners to further promote the KEYSTONE project. The scope of these materials is to showcase the project at various external events and attract the attention of targeted audience, stakeholders, and the general public. The printed materials are fully aligned with the KEYSTONE project's visual identity. They include the EU funding disclaimer, the European flag (emblem) to acknowledge EU support, and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) logo, as indicated in Section 17.2 Visibility- European flag and funding statement of the Grand Agreement. All printed materials can be found below in ANNEX B.

4.5.1 Roll-up

While a preliminary roll-up was designed and produced to accompany the kick-off meeting of the project, a second, more advanced version was created in M6 of the project and 1 copy per partner was distributed during the in-person Steering Committee meeting in Novara, Italy. The final version of the roll-up is also

available on the KEYSTONE website in the *Resources* section, where a dedicated area has been created for all project dissemination materials. The roll-up is provided in PDF format, making it easy to reprint as needed. The roll-up design effectively amplifies the project's main message, showing a truck on a highway and aiming to showcase the reference to the logistics and transport industries at a glance. Its prominent messaging is designed to engage audiences at events and presentations. The three main bullets, styled in KEYSTONE's colour palette, emphasise the project's key goals and objectives. Additionally, a QR code linking directly to the KEYSTONE website is included, alongside social media profiles and contact information. The figure in ANNEX B illustrates the KEYSTONE roll-up.

4.5.2 Poster

The first edition of the project poster was created, designed, printed, and distributed to project partners in M6, alongside with the roll-up, during the SC meeting in Novara, Italy. Following the same guidelines as the roll-up, the poster adheres to the project's visual identity and aligns with the project's colour scheme and font. The project website, social media channels, EU funding disclaimers, EU flag, and UKRI logo are prominent to acknowledge the EU and UKRI support. The primary aim of the poster is to serve as a visual tool at workshops and events, such as the Focus Group Discussions, to disseminate the project's key principles to stakeholders, members of the KEYSTONE community (both potential and existing), the scientific community, and the general public. The poster is designed to be adaptable to various events, allowing for the inclusion of additional details, such as date, venue, or other relevant information. The poster is also available online in the *Disseminations Materials* section of the project website. The two figures in ANNEX B present the poster's design and showcase its use in the second Focus Group Discussion.

4.5.3 Brochure

The KEYSTONE brochure was created in M12 of the project, ahead of its originally planned release in year 2. Due to active participation in various events and conferences from the very early stage of the project, all consortium partners agreed it would be beneficial to showcase the KEYSTONE activities in a summarised, informative, and interactive brochure that project partners can present. The brochure was designed to provide stakeholders and the targeted audience with additional information about KEYSTONE, including a description of its technical solution of KEYSTONE, the web app application, and its main characteristics. All partners contributed to the creation of the content and design of the brochure. As with all offline communication materials produced, the brochure adheres to the project's branding guidelines, including colour and font, as well as for funding disclaimer, EU emblem, and UKRI logo. The final page of the brochure introduces the KEYSTONE consortium partners, the social media accounts of the project, and a QR directing users to the registration form for joining the KEYSTONE community. This approach aims to promote the project efficiently, quickly, and effectively while increasing stakeholder engagement. In total, 600 copies of the brochure were printed and equally distributed to all consortium partners during the Steering Committee meeting held in Altea, Spain, in M12 of the project, also reaching the project's KPI.

4.6 Publications

No publications were expected to be submitted during the first year of the KEYSTONE project. However, a KEYSTONE profile⁶ has been created on the Zenodo data repository of OpenAIRE. This platform enables “green” open access to all publications, ensuring that the KEYSTONE findings will remain accessible even after the project's completion. These publications will significantly contribute to the academic dialogue by

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/keystone-project-eu/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

promoting the development of a sustainable, efficient, smart and secure system for data exchange in transport and logistics, paving the way for further research advancements in these fields.

4.6.1 Conference Paper

No publications were initially expected during the first year of the KEYSTONE project. However, project partners proactively presented already two conference papers, demonstrating the consortium's commitment to enhancing the project's visibility and impact while laying a foundation for engagement with the academic community.

During the TRA 2024 in Dublin, Ireland, the following paper was presented:

1. "Knowledgeable comprehensive and fully integrated smart solution for resilient, sustainable and optimised transport operations", authored by Giulia Renzi, Piergiuseppe Di Gregorio (UNIMORE), Zoi Petrakou, Alexandros Papacharalamous, Alexandros Georgakopoulos (Aethon Engineering Single Member P.C.), Camille Leotta, Andrea Mutti, (T Bridge-Spa), Fabrizio Borgogna (Gruber Logistics)

During the 7th Sustainable Mobility Conference in Greece (CSuM) in Plastira's Lake in Karditsa, Greece, the following paper was presented:

2. "KEYSTONE: Transforming the European Transport Ecosystem through Data-Driven Strategies, Operations, and Interoperability", authored by Prof Alexeis Garcia Perez, Prof Andrew Jones, Prof Kevin Broughton (Coventry University), Giulia Renzi, Paulo Cantillano Lizana (ICOOR), Zoi Petrakou, Alexandros Papacharalamous, Alexandros Georgakopoulos, Charis Koutsis (Aethon Engineering Single Member P.C.)

The papers are currently pending publication in the conference proceedings, and for this reason, they are not yet available for the Zenodo repository. Once published, they will be uploaded to the KEYSTONE Zenodo community, fully compliant with copyright requirements.

4.6.2 Journal Papers

At the halfway point of the KEYSTONE project, consortium partners have not yet published any journal papers. As it was highlighted in the *D6.3 - Communication & Dissemination plan and visual identity handbook*, the journal publications are planned towards the final year of the project, as they will present more relevant findings related to the technical solutions KEYSTONE aims to develop. As KEYSTONE is beginning to progress more on the technical level and as more and more substantial findings become available, journal papers will serve as an effective means of effectively showcasing the project's results. So far, the project results were not mature enough. The journal publications are expected in the second and third year of the project; however, to provide more significant results, the possibility of publishing two journal papers in year 3 of the project will be considered.

4.7 Events

The consortium has already taken part in many external and internal events, conferences, trade fairs, focus discussion groups, and other in-person meetings involving target stakeholders.

4.7.1 Project Events

Up to M17, three project events took place, aiming to engage representatives from logistics, transport and enforcement authorities in the project activities and involve them in the KEYSTONE stakeholders community. The events served as opportunities to present the project's progress and objectives while fostering a dialogue between project partners and the stakeholders.

The first project event took place on 28 November 2023 (M6) during the second in-person Steering Committee meeting at CIM Spa Headquarters in Novara, Italy. The event was structured as an FGD with the participation of ten high-ranking representatives of the three main industries (logistics, enforcement authorities and freight operators). Project partners had the opportunity to inform them about the projects' progress and benefit from the stakeholder's valuable insights and feedback.

The second event was also formed as an FGD and took place on 25 January 2024 (M8) at the School of Civil Engineering of the Technical University of Madrid (UPM). This event aimed to identify the needs and obstacles of the transport and logistics operators within the national scope of Spain and highlight the main challenges, barriers and needs of transport logistics at the national level. The FGD offered a platform for the exchange of ideas and expertise among the consortium partners and the present stakeholders.

The third project event was held on 16 May 2024 (M12), as CIM SpA organised a working day event focused on intermodality, sustainability and project planning ideas. KEYSTONE project partners had the opportunity to showcase the project activities to a delegation of Sorbonne University and presented them with how digitisation is reshaping transport and logistics activities.

4.7.2 External Events

By M17 of the project, KEYSTONE partners have participated in various external events, workshops, and meetings at national, European, and international levels. Participation in external events has significantly impacted the project's visibility, and the partners involved have successfully communicated the project's progress and primary goals. A project events calendar has been created, which is regularly updated to track upcoming events and conferences, ensuring better planning and collaboration among project partners. By M17, KEYSTONE partners represented the project's activities in 14 events, overreaching the project's target and nearly doubling the KPIs set for the entire project duration. By the midway of the project, KEYSTONE partners had participated in the following events:

1. 2023 STA Annual Conference & Innovation Awards, 26 October 2023, Milan (Italy) by STA;
2. NAPCORE Mobility Data (National Access Point Coordination Organization for Europe), 07-09 November 2023, Budapest (Hungary) by Aethon Engineering;
3. FEDeRATED Project Final Event, 30 November 2023, Brussels (Belgium) by Aethon Engineering;
4. Knowledge Exchange Workshop, 07 December 2023, Brussels (Belgium) by UNIMORE, Gruber Logistics, Aethon Engineering;
5. 3rd Spanish Smart Roads Forum, 19-21 December 2023, Madrid (Spain) by AEC;
6. LetEXPO- Logistics Eco Transport Trade 2024, 12-15 March 2024, Verona (Italy) by Cefriel, CIM Spa, RINA, Gruber Logistics;
7. Connecting Europe Days 2024, 02-05 April 2024, Brussels (Belgium) by Aethon Engineering, CIM Spa;
8. TRA (Transport Research Arena), 15-18 April 2024, Dublin (Ireland) by UNIMORE, Aethon Engineering, Gruber Logistics, STA, Etelätär Innovation;
9. Presentation at Alfonso X el Sabio University, 30 May 2024, Madrid (Spain) by AEC;
10. Transforming Road Mobility, 09-11 July 2024, Toledo (Spain) by AEC;
11. 7th Conference on Sustainable Mobility 2024 (CSuM), 04-06 September 2024, Plastira's Lake, Karditsa (Greece) by Aethon Engineering;
12. 16th ITS World Congress 2024, 16-20 September 2024, Dubai (UAE) by ICOOR, TTS Italia;
13. InnoTrans 2024, 24-27 September 2024, Berlin (Germany) by Coventry University;
14. STA Annual Conference & Innovation Awards 2024, 07 November 2024, Madrid (Spain) by STA, UPM, AEC.

5. Next Steps: PM18 Onward

For the next 18 months, it is important to strategically plan communication and dissemination activities to ensure the success of the communication and dissemination until the end of the project - and beyond its duration. As the majority of the project's KPIs have been achieved and also over-exceeded, the main goal of the KEYSTONE partners is to keep up the momentum, ensuring communication activities maintain a strong engagement with the targeted audience and continued visibility that aligns with the project's key objectives through to completion. The project has gained high interest from audience outside the EU borders, as for instance a strong interest from US audience. To capitalize on this interest, it would be beneficial to receive an invitation for a US based conference, explore networking opportunities, and further enhance the project's visibility. Additionally, it would be also beneficial if CINEA or DG MOVE, could consider inviting KEYSTONE to any relevant event organized in the US, aligned with the project's objectives. By taking these steps, we can ensure sustained impact across the project's duration and continued collaboration. Moving forward, project partners will prioritise and focus on the following activities:

- Apply for the Horizon Results Booster⁷ to boost the dissemination and exploitation of the KEYSTONE results to the market and be ready to convert the KEYSTONE project findings into significant outcomes;
- Promoting the *KEYSTONE In Action Newsletter* internally and also externally through relevant platforms to encourage more subscriptions;
- The second poster edition will be published at the end of year 2, when more technical development is expected to be available, allowing to include more technical information and results about the design of the web app and its structure;
- One more conference paper will be presented to meet the project's KPIs;
- Two journals-papers will be published after year 2 of the project's duration, reflecting the progress made and providing specified findings from the project.

⁷ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu>

6. Conclusions

The D6.4 Communication & Dissemination plan update has provided a detailed report of KEYSTONE's communication and dissemination activities until M17 of the project and outlined the project's strategy for the upcoming halfway review of the project⁸. During its first half, the KEYSTONE project has achieved strong visibility and recognition among diverse audiences, driven by the high engagement of all partners in communication and dissemination activities and the excellent visual brand identity. The priority moving forward will be to continue building on the successful communication strategy already in place while refining certain aspects and introducing additional activities to ensure the project's KPIs are overreached and complemented. The next update of these actions will be presented in *D6.5 – Final communication and dissemination report* (M36, May 2026), along with all the actions discussed and foreseen in the current deliverable.

⁸ EU Funds. (2021, September 20)

7. Annex A

7.1.1 LinkedIn Analytics Year 1 (M1-M12)

7.1.2 LinkedIn Analytics (M12-M17)

7.2 ANNEX B

7.2.1 Brochure Design

Vision

The development of KEYSTONE's vision towards more sustainable, efficient and safe transport logistics will be achieved through the following set of innovative actions:

- Tailored and standardised digital solutions from existing use cases to the transport system.
- Development of a web app solution implementing a new API standard and Plug & Play Framework.
- Reduced operational costs and CO2 footprint, to complete multi-lingual and verified documentation digitally.
- A safer data transfer system and promotion of CCAM technologies for safe, secure and efficient transport flows.

Meet Our Team

KEYSTONE Consortium

The KEYSTONE Consortium comprises a diverse range of entities, including universities, research centres, industry leaders, logistics companies, SMEs and non-profit organisations. Our enthusiastic team of dedicated individuals collaborates closely to drive innovation and success in the project.

Join the KEYSTONE Community

Follow us

- KEYSTONE_EU
- KEYSTONE_EU

www.keystone-project.com

One Step Closer to the Digitisation of Transport Logistics

What Makes Us Different

KEYSTONE's digital solutions consist of an innovative API standard and a web app solution, both implementing a Plug & Play Framework, that will accelerate the data sharing between logistics operators and transport enforcement authorities based on a federated approach.

Our web app solution brings to life a new API standard and Plug & Play Framework.

Goal

The overarching goal of KEYSTONE is the development and conceptualisation of a sustainable, efficient and safe transport system, which allows enforcement authorities to access data for compliance checks between enforcement authorities and logistics operators.

- Information**
Research & Innovation Action (RIA)
- Duration**
From 01 June 2023 to 31 May 2026
- Funding**
European Commission, United Kingdom Research & Innovation (UKRI)

KEYSTONE In a nutshell

KEYSTONE develops a seamless data-sharing environment and API standard and allows enforcement authorities, freight terminals and logistics operators to access data for compliance checks in the transport of goods and passengers.

KEYSTONE Pilots

The two project pilots cover a geographical 'boom' extending from Northern Italy to the Benelux coast, often referred to informally as the 'Blue Banana'.

KEYSTONE Countries

Funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

7.2.2 Roll-Up & Poster Design

A) Roll-Up

B) Poster

C) Roll-up during the presentation of AEC at the Alfonso X el Sabio University in Madrid, Spain.

D) Poster during one of the FDGs in Madrid, Spain.

KEYSTONE

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